

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE IMPACT OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON MENTAL HEALTH

Salamova Aygul

Teacher of the Department of General Sciences of ADPU Sheki branch

Abstract

Climate change has become a growing global crisis. To date, researchers studying the effects of climate change on human health have mostly considered its effects on physical health. However, climate change may also exacerbate social and environmental risk factors for mental health and psychosocial problems, resulting in new mental health problems. It can also make things worse for people with existing mental health problems. Therefore, there is a need to provide mental health and psychosocial support to prepare for and respond to climate change. The purpose of this article is to explore the relationship between climate change and mental health, and to make mental health and psychosocial well-being a focal point of climate action. At the same time, measures should be taken in time to prevent the impact of climate change on mental health from becoming a serious security problem.

Keywords: climate change, mental health, depression, stress disorder, eco-concern, security measures

Human life has an inseparable connection with nature and environment. Even a short walk in nature is enough to feel the contributions of nature to mental and physical health. Although nature and people exist within each other, they constantly influence each other. Therefore, a change in one will directly or indirectly change the other.

Mental health and well-being are linked to the climate crisis. The demographic and biological characteristics of the individual, as well as factors related to pre-existing mental and physical health, personal values and attitudes, social relationships and values in which they are involved, interact with wider social networks. All of these are shaped by living and working conditions, such as access to safe housing, water and food security, access to health services, and livelihoods. Broader environmental, socioeconomic, political, and cultural influences affect all layers. Therefore, since the layers specified in the model and the determinants that form it are interconnected and interact, a deterioration in one layer due to a negative climate-related effect affects all other layers.

"Climate change both caused by human-caused emissions of greenhouse gases which he set in motion global warming, but also includes large-scale changes in weather patterns as a result" [5].

"And mental health of a person it is characterized by its mental state, the regulation of its behavior, and the correct formation of its character under the influence of social and biological factors. Mental health manifests itself in a person's attitude towards himself and the people around him, in general, in his attitude towards various events, social and economic difficulties throughout his life" [6].

Mental health, a fundamental human right, affects how we think, feel and act, and underpins our ability to make decisions, form relationships and shape the world we live in. Mental health is an integral part of health and well-being and is more than the absence of mental illness. Mental health can be defined as a person's ability to think, learn and live with their own emotions and the reactions of others.

The groups most affected by the mental and physical health effects of climate change are: emergency workers, rural populations, children, the elderly, women, people of low socioeconomic status, the homeless, outdoor workers, people exposed to racism, immigrants, and existing health conditions.

"The negative effects of climate change on human health can be classified as follows:

- ✓ heat-related deaths
- ✓ heart, circulatory, vascular and respiratory diseases due to the increase in temperature
- ✓ lung disorders from air pollution from hot weather related fires
- ✓ hygiene problems due to lack of water
- ✓ increase in epidemic diseases
- ✓ psychological disorders" [1, p. 79].

The mental health effects of acute, subacute and chronic events caused by climate change are categorized as direct and indirect effects. Direct effects are conditions caused by physical causes. Indirect impacts occur as a result of the negative impact of climate change on people's living standards and infrastructure.

The most direct impacts of climate change occur after extreme weather events, called extreme events, and the resulting floods, hurricanes, and fires. The most common mental health problems after extreme weather events are depression and post-traumatic stress disorder. Stress is a physiological reaction that occurs when a person feels unable to respond and adapt to a certain situation. Therefore, climate-related stress can lead to an increase in stress-related problems such as substance abuse, anxiety disorders, and depression. Stress can also be accompanied by feelings of vulnerability, helplessness, sadness, and hopelessness.

Common health effects of stress include conditions such as high blood pressure, heart disease, obesity, and diabetes. The physical damage of climate change is often much lower than the psychological damage. Although people can cope with climate disasters, they can sometimes experience serious mental health problems such as climate-related depression, post-traumatic stress and anxiety. This is

because at the same time, as a result of climate change, people can lose their homes, jobs and property, or witness deaths, and can have a traumatic effect on human psychology. The more severe and intense a person's exposure to traumatic events, the greater the likelihood of serious mental health problems.

Subacute or long-term climate changes last for months or years and include events such as droughts and prolonged heat waves. These effects can cause a strong emotional response in those experiencing the effects of the climate crisis, both directly and indirectly. In this sense, the change that is clearly related to the climate crisis is global warming and an increase in average temperature. Heat waves, increase in average temperature and changes in weather conditions that people are used to are associated with increased aggression, physical and psychological fatigue, and suicides. Aggression and antisocial behavior increase as the temperature rises. Heat waves are known to affect mood and mental well-being, disrupting concentration and making people feel more tired. As a result of extreme temperature increase, the reduction of food and drink supplies and the increase of infectious disease factors can cause psychological distress in people such as fear and anxiety. In addition, heat negatively affects cognitive function, which reduces the ability to resolve nonviolent conflict and predisposes a person to violence.

Indirect effects of climate change include economic losses, displacement and forced migration, competition over scarce resources, and violence. Deforestation, glacier retreat, river loss, desertification, water scarcity, increased infectious diseases, and biomass loss affect the habitats and daily lives of communities, causing the loss of spatial and cultural characteristics. All changes and losses can have negative effects on physical and mental health. Long and severe periods of drought can make it difficult for affected communities to access water and food, displace communities with loss of livelihoods and livelihoods, and cause psychological problems associated with the loss of homes and social networks. Economic crises can occur after environmental changes and lead to an increase in suicide rates and other mental and behavioral disorders.

The direct and indirect effects of the climate crisis can also lead to the exacerbation of existing mental illnesses by preventing access to health services and disabling social support systems.

One of the best ways to describe the perceptual effects of climate change is a sense of "loss." As climate change irreversibly changes the places where people live, many people feel as if they have lost a place that is important to them.

This psychological phenomenon parallels a sense of desolation and loss similar to that experienced by people forced to migrate from their home environment.

Another fundamental loss is the loss of personal identity in relation to the mundane aspects of daily life. When a home is damaged or destroyed as a result of climate change, losing valuables can create an environment where an individual's sense of self and identity can be significantly disrupted. This is because

objects symbolize who we are, especially important moments in life and family relationships.

Loss of professional identity due to climate change is one of the most important factors that negatively affect the psychology of an individual. Loss of profession is associated with an increased risk of depression after climate change and natural disasters.

Gradual and long-term changes in climate can cause a range of different emotions, such as sadness, anxiety, fear, anger, powerlessness, helplessness, guilt or exhaustion.

New insights have entered our literature as different fields of science and perspectives come together to understand the effects of the climate crisis on our psychology. One of them is the concept of eco-concern. Eco-concern, which is based on two different fields and can sometimes be referred to as eco-concern or environmental concern, is a term that originates from concepts of concern that we often hear in the fields of natural science (ecology) and psychology.

Anxiety is broadly defined as a state of intense anxiety accompanied by fear of the possibility of a future disaster. It is more about the uncertainty and unpredictability of the future and the possibility of a future situation that poses a threat to man.

Eco-anxiety is the constant fear of environmental catastrophe due to monitoring the inevitable impact of climate change, and thus concern about the future of one's self and future generations. Based on this, we see that eco-anxiety has not yet been recognized as a disease, but has entered our lives as a subtype of anxiety. However, in general, anxiety arises from irrational fears, but when it comes to eco-anxiety, we see that it arises from negative events that may occur. This shows the seriousness of the situation. A person is experiencing eco-anxiety if symptoms such as anger, inability to control anxiety, fear, inability to stop thinking about them, and difficulty falling asleep persist, especially when thinking about climate change and other global environmental conditions.

Although eco-anxiety is not currently considered a medical condition, the APA defined it as a "chronic fear of environmental doom". The difficulty in categorising such a condition comes from the many ways in which it can be expressed. Some people have everyday episodes of grief and despair, others exhibit sudden panic attacks while some have even made the big decision to not have children because they believe it may be unethical due to future quality of life [3, p.3].

Eco-anxiety is not considered a "disorder" or a disease. Because this anxiety is a natural and understandable result of the person being directly or indirectly affected by the changes in the world they are in. However, with eco-anxiety, people can sometimes engage in some avoidance behaviors in their daily lives, and this can lead to other psychological problems over time as the intensity and severity of anxiety increases.

Eco-anxiety can be seen in any individual who is sensitive to the environment. However, some groups are more prone to eco-anxiety due to different reasons such as living conditions and future expectations. These groups can be summarized as follows:

- displaced people

- people living in drought-stricken regions
- those working in the field during environmental disasters
- people with anxiety disorder or major depressive disorder
- low income groups
- young children, adolescents, and older adults

Ecological emotions are emotions that mediate and relate to the concept of eco-concern. Emotions related to ecology can be listed as follows: guilt, sadness, trauma, despair, anger.

Psychological symptoms of climate change include:

- **sadness and despair:** emotional changes such as feeling constantly sad and hopeless about the future, increased stress levels, anxiety or depression
- **physical symptoms:** physical stress symptoms such as sleep disturbances, headaches, upset stomach, loss of energy and general weakness
- **social isolation:** social isolation, decreased social interaction
- **concentration difficulties:** difficulty concentrating on daily tasks
- **reduced contact with nature:** decrease in connection with the natural environment or loss of interest in natural areas
- **obsession about climate:** thoughts and constant worries about climate change.

Climate change will affect human mental health in many ways, and these effects are likely to increase. It is necessary to take measures to reduce global warming or to develop mechanisms to cope with the difficulties that arise through adaptation. Reducing greenhouse gases, reducing energy consumption based on fossil fuels, developing and using alternative and sustainable efficient energy sources, ending the destruction that reduces green areas, and making plans such as reducing carbon footprint are some of the things that need to be done to prevent climate change, global warming and its effects.

"In order to overcome the impact of climate change on mental health, the existence of climate change must be accepted, beliefs and personal opinions must be put aside, and scientific evidence must be trusted. Considering that climate change has negative effects not only on physical health, but also on mental health, more attention should be paid to research on the topic. The number of national and international conferences should be increased, the public should be informed through communication channels such as social media and television. Special fields and, if necessary, departments should be created against the negative effects of climate psychology. As part of the comprehensive fight against climate change, education should start at the kindergarten level. This will be useful in psychological preparation. More emphasis should be placed on psychological support initiatives, awareness and information programmes. Impacts on psychological health must be addressed globally, covering all risks. We should also raise our environmental awareness to a high level and focus on guiding other individuals in the society correctly in this regard" [4, p.586].

Another suggestion to reduce the psychological effects of climate change is psychological adaptation. Psychological adaptation involves a series of response behaviors such as accepting the serious threats and consequences of climate change and the global crisis. It is a process in which people develop coping strategies to face the threat and consequences of climate change instead of avoiding it and to manage the emotions and thoughts that arise. It also requires behavioral and psychological participation in which people change their behaviors and lifestyles to reduce the threat and protect themselves. Active hope supports people's psychological adaptation to the process. Active hope increases the ability to actively engage in adaptation behaviors to mitigate the effects of climate change rather than waiting for someone else to take on the task of addressing the climate change problem. The important issue here is that hope alone will not provide sufficient protection against the increasing risks of climate change. This active process is completed when the reality and magnitude of the problem are accepted, plans are determined to solve the problem, and actions are taken on the subject.

"In the researches of recent years, it is very rightly noted that the ecological crisis is the revenge of nature itself against the merciless attitude towards nature. According to the three big "culprits" (society, scientific and technical revolution, man) of the aggravation of environmental problems, researchers show three ways to solve them. These are socio-political, scientific-technical and moral pedagogical ways.

The first way, the harmonious development of society and nature requires the implementation of a socio-economic policy that provides for the creation of complex environmental programs;

The second way, suggests finding a scientific-technical solution to specific ecological problems.

The third way, implies the formation of ecological culture, ecological awareness and ecological behavior of the personality" [2, p.203].

Thus, ecological policy, ecological economy and ecological ethics interact with each other and constitute ecological culture and ecological civilization as a whole.

According to the order of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Ilham Aliyev, 2024 was declared the "Year of Solidarity for the Green World" in the Republic of Azerbaijan in order to strengthen international solidarity in the global fight against climate change.

From November 11 to 22, 2024, Baku hosted the 29th session of the Conference of the Parties to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (COP 29), which is considered one of the largest and most influential events in the world. The event, which was attended by 72 thousand participants from 196 countries, including 80 presidents, vice-presidents and prime ministers, attracted attention in terms of its grandeur, high level of organization and relevance of the discussed topics. The world gathered in Azerbaijan to jointly determine ways to solve environmental problems. The events held within the framework of COP29, the bitter consequences of natural disasters

caused by climate problems, "green" energy and other topics were followed with interest by the public, our scientists and experts in various fields. COP29 will play an important role in reducing the psychological effects of climate change, informing the public about it and preparing people psychologically for future changes.

In conclusion, the relationship between climate change and human psychology is an issue that can harm both society and individuals, both individually and socially. Everyone must do their part to raise awareness and develop systemic solutions.

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